

Peroxidases. Part II. The Influence of the Concentration of Substrate (Hydroquinone), of Hydrogen Peroxide, P_H and other Factors on the Activity of the Peroxidase of Chow Chow (*Sechium Edule*).

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In the present paper several of the important factors which influence the activities of peroxidases have been studied in detail, the peroxidase activities being determined by the method described previously (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 479). The vegetable commonly known as Chow Chow (*Sechium Edule* S. W., N. O. *Cucurbitaceae*), is found to be extraordinarily rich in this enzyme, and all experiments recorded in this paper have been carried out with an enzyme extract prepared from this particular vegetable. Several attempts were made to prepare the enzymes both from the Jhinga (*Luffa acutangula*) and the chow chow fruits in as pure a condition as possible by the usual methods described by Willstätter and Stoll (*Annalen*, 1918, 416, 21), but a certain amount of rotting invariably set in during the preliminary process of soaking the thin slices of the vegetables in flowing water for several days, as recommended by these authors, for the purpose of removing the simpler products by dialysis through the cell walls themselves. A material which may be considered to be an extract of the oxidising enzymes practically free from all foreign matter, prepared by the method described below, has, however, been found to be very suitable for the purposes of these investigations. The fresh vegetable, cut into very thin slices, is washed in running water for a few hours, and then made into pulp with an ordinary mutton chopper tinned on the inside and paraffined all over to prevent the sap from coming into contact with the metal. The pulp is gently squeezed through muslin bags, an average chow chow fruit, weighing about 250 g., yielding in this way 120-140 c.c. of a nearly colourless, and somewhat turbid liquid. This was now dialysed through a parchment bag in a tall beaker at 10°, in a refrigerator, the water to which a few drops of toluene had been added being frequently replaced. The operation normally required 4

days at the end of which period the dialysed sap became clear and its osmotic pressure had greatly diminished. It was now centrifuged to remove all suspended particles, and finally filtered through paper pulp into a bottle containing a few drops of toluene and preserved in the refrigerator. An extract prepared in this manner retained its peroxidase activity perfectly unimpaired and gave the same titre value with decinormal thiosulphate even at the end of one month as when it was freshly made. The pH of this liquid, determined in all cases with the quinhydrone electrode, usually ranged between 4.5 and 4.6, but in rare instances it has been found to go down as low as 4.33 or rise as high as 4.86.

The extract, in the case of chow chow, is found to contain the enzymes in a very concentrated form, and the normal reaction with hydroquinone proceeds so rapidly that equilibrium is attained almost immediately. * The undiluted sap could not therefore be used for the purpose of studying the kinetics of this oxidation reaction, and a few preliminary experiments had to be made to determine the precise concentration and volume of the enzyme solution which was most suitable for these studies. The course of the reaction was followed with (a) the undiluted sap, (b) the sap diluted with an equal volume of water, (c) sap diluted with three times its volume of water and (d) sap diluted with seven times its volume of water, corresponding respectively to the original half, one-fourth, and one-eighth of the concentration of the enzyme in the sap.

FIG 1.

* In this preparation, the peroxidase was not contaminated with oxygenase as no oxidation was found to occur in the absence of hydrogen peroxide.

It would be seen from the results given in Tables I and II that a dilution corresponding to a fourth of the enzyme concentration of the undiluted sap works most satisfactorily. A 15 minutes reaction period was found to be the most suitable, while a volume of 5 c.c. of the dilute enzyme solution which produced the maximum effect under the conditions of our experiments, was chosen in all cases. All reactants were measured directly from a refrigerator maintaining a constant temperature of 13°. The results are shown in Tables I and II and in Fig. 1, 2 and 3.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

Effect of the hydrogen peroxide concentration on peroxidase activity—Bach (*Ber.*, 1904 37, 37-37), Willstätter and Weber (*Annalen*, 1923, 449, 175) and Mann (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 918) have shown that excess of hydrogen peroxide inhibits the activity of the peroxidases, and in larger quantities, destroys it altogether, and in our experiments with the peroxidase of *Luffa acutangula* described previously, we have been able to confirm these conclusions. It is, therefore, essential to determine carefully the proper concentration of hydrogen peroxide to be employed in each experiment which is calculated to prevent any destruction of the enzyme, and at the same time to produce the maximum effect. Several experiments were made in which the concentration of H_2O_2 was varied, while all the other factors were kept constant. The precipitated quinhydrone was collected on a coarse Jena sintered glass filter and estimated volumetrically according to the usual method. From the

results given in Table III and in Fig. 4, it will be evident that under the conditions of our experiments, the maximum activity is

attained when the amount of hydrogen peroxide added is 2 c.c. of 1 p. c. strength (0.02 g. in 13 c.c. of reaction mixture), and this concentration of H₂O₂ was therefore adhered to in all the subsequent experiments.

Effect of the concentration of substrate at constant pH.—In the course of an interesting series of experiments of an allied type on the peroxidase of horse-radish roots, Getchell and Walton (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1931, 91, 419) have shown that at pH 6 and with pyrogallol substrate, the concentration of maximum activity is 10 dg. per 100 c.c., other conditions, *e. g.*, strength of the enzyme solution, etc., remaining unaltered. The usual curve with mg. of purpurogallin plotted as ordinate and dg. of pyrogallol plotted as abscissa, shows a peak at 10 dg. and falls off rapidly after the concentration has reached this limit. On account of the limited solubility of hydroquinone, it was not possible to carry on our experiments beyond a concentration of 4.5 per cent. A citrate buffer of pH 5.2, was used and a constant volume was added for each experiment. The hydroquinone was weighed out in each case, instead of adding it in solution, and the total volume of the reaction mixture was thus kept constant. The curve does not show any well defined peak, and the activity seems to remain constant when the concentration of

the substrate is between 0.25 and 0.35 at the total constant volume of 13 c.c. (cf. Table IV and Fig. 5).

FIG. 5.

Activity-pH relationship.—McIlvaine's citrate buffer, providing a convenient range from pH 2.2 to pH 8.0, was prepared by using the purest citric acid crystals and sodium phosphate (Sørensen's $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). 5–6 C.c. of the buffer were measured into a 50 c.c. beaker, and 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. H_2O_2 , 0.3 g. of hydroquinone and 5 c.c. of the enzyme solution successively added, the total volume being kept constant in each case. The reaction was stopped by adding 2 c.c. of 2N-HCl. With hydroquinone substrate, the activity is perceptible even in $N/10$ solutions of HCl with a pH of about 1.07. The optimum pH for the peroxidase of horse-radish has been given as 7 when pyrogallol is used as the substrate, while with guaiacol it lies between 5 and 5.2, and with *o*-cresol, between 3.5 and 3 (cf. Bansi and Ucko, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, 159, 235). It can be seen from our results, that with the hydroquinone substrate, the maximum activity of chow chow peroxidase lies between 4.8 and 5.2 in the acid region, whether the raw or the dialysed sap is used. Wieland and Sutter (*Ber.*, 1928, 61, 1060), proceeding in a different way, find the optimum pH to be 4.6 for the oxygenase of *Lactarius vellereus* (fungus) which

FIG. 6.

FIG. 7.

FIG. 8.

autoxidises quinol with the production of hydrogen peroxide. Special precautions had to be taken to prevent the aerial oxidation of hydroquinone solutions which showed signs of oxidation by turning brown even when the *pH* just exceeded 6.6, and all experiments in the alkaline regions of *pH* and those approaching alkalinity were therefore carried out with a current of nitrogen bubbling through the liquid. The results are summarised in Tables V, VI and VII, and in Fig. 6, 7 and 8.

Inhibition of the reaction by HCl, and the influence of poisons like KCN and HgCl₂, on the activity.—Experiments carried out in normal (*pH* 0.10), decinormal (*pH* 1.07) and centinormal (*pH* 2.02) HCl solutions showed that with dilute solutions of the enzyme the reactivity was practically nil. When, however, the enzyme solution was concentrated, *e. g.*, when the undiluted sap was employed, the action was observed to be fairly rapid even in *N/100-HCl*. In such cases, the reaction was found to be completely stopped only by the addition of 2*N-HCl* until the final solution had become approximately *N/5* with respect to it.

The activity of the enzyme is inhibited completely by KCN of *M/10,000* concentration, while in solutions of *M/100,000* concentration, the activity is almost unaffected. Mercuric chloride does not seem to have so marked an effect in poisoning the peroxidase; under similar conditions, the peroxidase showed signs of considerable activity even after the addition of a solution of mercuric chloride of *M/1000* concentration. The results are given in Tables VIII and IX.

Results.

TABLE I. (*cf.* Fig. 1—3).

To 7 c. c. of buffer (*pH* 5.6) was added 2 c. c. of 1% H₂O₂, 0.3 g. of hydroquinone, 5 c.c. of sap, and the reaction was stopped by the addition of 2 c.c. of 2*N-HCl* (Total vol., 16 c.c. at 13°).

Time in min.	...	3	5	10	15	20	25	40	60
<i>N/10-Thioisulphate in c.c.</i>									
(1) Undiluted sap	...	18.1	18.1	18.9	18.85	18.85	18.85	18.85	18.85
(2) Sap diluted with its own vol. of water	...	15.65	19.2	19.2	19.2	...	19.2	19.2	19.2
(3) Sap diluted with three times its vol. of water	...	6.6	10.15	15.4	17.7	19.25	19.2	19.1	19.2

When (3) was left over night (16 hours) in the refrigerator, the value obtained was the same, *viz.*, 19.20 c.c. The pH in the above experiments was maintained at 5.6.

At pH 5.2, 5 c.c. of sap (1:3) gave quinhydrone in a 15 minutes reaction period corresponding to 10.25 c.c. of thiosulphate, while under identical conditions, the same volume of sap (1:7) gave quinhydrone corresponding to 4.62 c.c., showing thereby that the reaction is greatly slowed down by dilution.

TABLE II.

Experiments with varying quantities of enzyme solution (1:3) were made using 5 c.c. of buffer (pH 5.6) and 2 c.c. of 1 per cent. H_2O_2 , 2 c.c. of 2N-HCl being finally added to stop the reaction. In all the experiments the volume of the reaction mixture was 15 c.c. and of wt. hydroquinone, 0.3g.

Vol. of sap (c.c.)	...	1	2	3	4	5	6	10
Vol. of buffer	...	5	5	5	5	5	5	nil
Water (c.c.)	...	5	4	3	2	1	0	1
N/10-Thiosulphate	...	0.35	3.60	6.82	9.60	10.2	10.2	10.1

It is evident that 5 c.c. of the sap, diluted in the above proportion, has the maximum effect under the conditions of experiment given above.

TABLE III (*cf.* Fig. 4).

Effect of variation in the concentration of H_2O_2 (unbuffered).

H_2O_2 .	Hydroquinone.	Vol. of sap.	2N-Acid to stop reaction.	Water.	N/10-Thio-sulphate.
0.5c.c. (1%)	5 c.c. (4.4%)	5 c.c.	2 c.c.	2.5 c.c.	2.0 c.c.
				2.0	
1.0	"	"	"	2.0	4.60
1.5	"	"	"	1.5	7.40
2.0	"	"	"	1.0	9.70
3.0	"	"	"	0.0	7.40
2.0 c.c. (2%)	5 c.c.	"	"	1.0	5.55
2.5	"	"	"	0.5	3.8
3.0	"	"	"	0.0	3.0
3.5	"	"	1.5	0.0	2.45

The maximum activity is attained with 2 c.c. of H_2O_2 of 1% strength, and rapidly falls off afterwards.

TABLE IV (cf. Fig. 5).

The p_H having been kept constant at 5.2, the activity was measured at different concentrations of hydroquinone, the latter being weighed out each time. The reaction mixture contained 6 c.c. buffer, 5 c.c. sap, 2 c.c. of 1% H_2O_2 , with 2 c.c. 2N-HCl which was finally added to stop the reaction.

Wt. of hydroquinone	...	0.10	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.4	0.5	0.6
N/10-Thiosulphate (c.c.)	...	4.10	8.65	9.55	10.0	10.2	10.4	9.85	9.75	8.65

The activity is greatest when the amount of hydroquinone used is 0.35 g. and it can be taken to be almost the same for concentrations of hydroquinone between 0.25 and 0.35 in a total volume of 13 c.c. of the reaction mixture, excluding the volume of HCl added to stop the reaction.

Activity- p_H relationships.—Three sets of experiments were carried out with varying concentrations of hydroquinone for each set of experiments.

TABLE V (cf. Fig. 6).

(1) 6 C.c. buffer, 2 c.c. 1% H_2O_2 , 5 c.c. sap, diluted 4 times, 0.3 g. hydroquinone with the final addition of 2 c.c. 2N-HCl for stopping the reaction.

p_H	...	2.4	2.8	3.2	4.0	4.8	5.2	5.6	6.4	7.2	8.0
N/10-Thiosulphate (c.c.)	...	0.4	1.6	3.4	8.9	10.1	9.85	10.0	9.4	7.9	3.5

TABLE VI (cf. Fig. 7).

(2) 5 C.c. buffer, 5 c.c. H.Q. (0.22 g.), 5 c.c. diluted sap and finally 2 c.c. 2N-HCl.

p_H	...	2.4	2.8	3.2	4.0	4.8	5.2	5.6	6.4	7.2	8.0
N/10-Thiosulphate (c.c.)	...	1.80	4.27	7.0	9.2	9.65	9.85	9.0	7.65	3.4	0.55

TABLE VII (cf Fig. 8).

(3) 7 C.c. buffer, 2 c.c. H_2O_2 , 0.3 g. H.Q. 5 c.c. sap (undiluted and undialysed), and finally 2 c.c. 2N-HCl.

p_H	...	2.4	2.8	3.2	4.0	4.8	5.2	6.0	6.8	7.2	7.6	8.0
N/10-Thiosulphate (c.c.)	1.30	2.35	4.7	9.7	11.8	17.1	16.05	13.3	9.6	6.05	2.8	

Influence of HCN and $HgCl_2$.

TABLE VIII.

(1) See also Table VI for the effect due to variation of p_H).

Conc. of KCN in molality	...	0.01	0.01	0.001	0.0005	0.00033	0.0001	nil.
p_H	7.24	4.62
N/10-Thiosulphate (c.c.)	...	nil	nil	nil	2.90	5.00	9.8	9.8

TABLE IX.

Conc. of $HgCl_2$.	p_H .	N/10-Thiosulphate.	Activity of enzyme alone.
M/100	...	7.85	9.8
M/1000	3.95	9.25	9.8
M/10000	...	9.7	9.8